
Kinematic calibration of a novel two-axis solar tracker

Jun Wu*, Hao Ye, Yanling Tian

Abstract—This paper deals with the kinematic calibration of a two-axis over-constrained solar tracker. In an over-constrained mechanism, it is difficult to derive the constraint among geometric errors and then the accurate error model can not be achieved. This paper presents a new error modeling method with considering constraints among geometric errors to derive a complete, continuous and minimal model. The constraint among geometric errors are derived from an algebraic approach with strict theoretical proof. Furthermore, an iterative Tikhonov regularization method is presented for parameter identification and the iteration termination condition is related to the measurement noise. The traditional Tikhonov regularization method is a posterior method that depends on the measurement data in calibration, while the proposed regularization method is a prior method with clear physical meaning. The kinematic calibration of the two-axis solar tracker is used to validate the proposed methods. The orientation error of the solar tracker is reduced by more than 95% after kinematic calibration.

Note to Practitioners—The geometric error constraints are proven in the article to exist in an over-constrained two-axis solar tracker, which leads to the unsuitability of previous calibration methods. With our proposed method, the accuracy of the solar tracker has been improved by 95% after calibration. In our calibration, the error modeling method can be extended to other over-constrained robots, and the Tikhonov regularization method has good stability and accuracy in error identification. In future research, we will address the problem of deformation and joint clearance in kinematic calibration.

Index Terms—kinematic calibration, parallel mechanism, solar tracker, error model, parameter identification

I. INTRODUCTION

THE solar tracker is a device that orients a payload toward been widely applied in the concentrated solar collector and the photovoltaic collector [1][2]. Solar trackers can be divided into the single-axis tracker (the azimuth angle) and the two-axis tracker (the azimuth and solar altitude angles) [3]. Since at least two-axis are required to keep the orientation of the collectors perpendicular to the solar radiation, the two-axis solar tracker is more popular. The two-axis solar tracker is an automatic manipulator and the predominant two-axis trackers are commonly designed based on the serial mechanism. However, due to the low stiffness of the serial mechanism, the

stout pole and the heavy counterbalance are needed to support the payload, which leads to high power consumption [4]. Compared with the traditional serial mechanism, the parallel mechanism (PM), especially the over-constrained PM, has some advantages in the higher payload-to-weight ratio, higher stiffness and lower power dissipation. Thus, the solar tracker based on the PM has great potential for future development [5].

Accuracy is critical for the practical application of a solar tracker, and the kinematic calibration is a practical and cost-effective way to improve accuracy by compensating geometric errors in the controller [6]-[9]. The kinematic calibration requires an error model that relates to the geometric source errors and the pose errors of the moving platform (MP). In general, the geometric error modeling method includes three steps: 1) establish the geometric error model of each link and joint, 2) eliminate the motion errors in passive joints (passive errors), and 3) eliminate redundant errors to ensure errors' linear independence [10]. For the non-over-constrained PMs, passive errors are generally eliminated by projecting the pose error of the MP to the limbs' reciprocal system [11][12]. However, in the over-constrained structure, the passive errors cannot be determined by the projection method, since the limbs' reciprocal screw systems are not linearly independent of each other [13]. It is difficult to eliminate the passive errors in the error modeling of the over-constrained structure. In addition, the geometric error would be required to satisfy some constraint equations since the number of the closed-loop kinematic equations is larger than the number of passive joints in the over-constrained mechanism. In some over-constrained robots, passive errors are eliminated by the pseudo-inverse [14] or even ignored [15], which leads to closed-loop vector equations that may not be satisfied under geometric errors. Thus, the error model is not accurate and the accuracy of the end-effector is affected. In addition, some geometric error models are established by directly differentiating nominal kinematics [16], or implicit constraint among geometric errors [17]. However, the rationality of the error model is doubtful since the constraint among geometric errors is given without theoretical analysis.

Besides error modeling, another kernel step in kinematic calibration is parameter identification, which can be regarded as an optimization problem. In fact, the control parameter design problem also can be formulated as an optimization problem under constraints [18]. Stojanovic [19] proposed a parameter search based on cuckoo search to effectively search parameters of the cascade controllers. However, for the

Manuscript received Mar 13, 2024. This work is supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (Grant No. 52375502) and EU H2020 MSCA R&I Programme (no. 101022696).

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parameter identification in the kinematic calibration, some parameters are obtained by experiments such as the pose information of the measurement points. It is not like the control parameter design problem where smaller residuals are better.

In parameter identification, the most common practice is the least square (LS) method [20]. However, due to the ill-posed problem of the identification matrix, the result obtained by the LS method is easily disturbed by measurement noise, which is inevitable and affected by the measurement uncertainty caused by mechanism repeatability, measurement equipment and environmental noise [21]. For the parameter identification of stochastic nonlinear parameter varying systems, Stojanovic [22-24] proposed robust identification method and the Masreliez-Martin filter is used to suppress noise in state space. Furthermore, Stojanovic [25] presented an adaptive input design for identification of output error model. These methods are more suitable for parameter identification of dynamics. For the parameter identification in kinematic calibration, the Tikhonov regularization method is an effective approach to solve the ill-posed problem, which improves the stability of solutions by sacrificing a part of the unbiasedness of the LS solution [26]. The effect of the Tikhonov regularization method mainly depends on the appropriate selection of regularization parameters. In general, the regularization parameter is determined by the L-curve method [27] or the generalized cross-validation (GCV) method [28-30]. However, it is difficult to select the appropriate regularization parameters since the geometric errors are determined by single measurement data. In other words, traditional methods are the posterior method without any prior knowledge and are susceptible to inevitable measurement noise. In addition, the current regularization parameter has no clear physical meaning.

In this paper, the error model is derived by considering passive errors and constraints among geometric errors. The model can demonstrate the influence of the overdetermined problem in the over-constrained mechanism on the geometric error, and provides a reference for the accuracy design of the over-constrained mechanism. Furthermore, an iterative Tikhonov regularization method, where the iterative termination criterion has a clear physical meaning, is presented for parameter identification. The identification method is a prior method and has better identification stability and accuracy than the traditional Tikhonov regularization method.

This paper is organized as follows: Section II describes the structure and the kinematics of the solar tracker. Section III derives the geometric error model. Parameter identification and error compensation are proposed in Sections IV and V, respectively. Kinematic calibration results are reported in Section VI and conclusions are listed in Section VII.

II. STRUCTURE DESCRIPTION AND KINEMATICS

A. Structure description

The conventional two-axis solar tracker with a serial mechanism is similar to a 2-DOF RR (R is revolute joint) robot. In general, it has a vertical pole and a transversal pole mounted on the vertical pole. Due to the cantilever structure, the conventional solar tracker requires great torque for the actuators.

Based on the conventional two-axis solar tracker, a new 2-

DOF solar tracker, shown in Fig. 1, is created by introducing a simple 5R parallel manipulator. The 5R PM driven by two actuators is connected to the MP and the base by the universal (U) joint and revolute (R) joint, respectively. Since there are common constraints that restrict the 5R PM in one plane, the 5R PM and the corresponding 2-DOF solar tracker are over-constrained according to the definition of the over-constrained PM [31]. Moreover, the vertical pole and transversal pole are passive and the MP has two rotational DOFs.

B. Inverse Kinematics

Fig. 2 shows the schematic diagram of the two-axis solar tracker and the 5R planar PM. The 5R PM is connected to the MP and the base by U joint and R joint, as shown in Fig. 2(a). The base right-handed coordinate system $M-XYZ$ is attached to the base. The Z -axis is vertical to the plane of the base, and the X -axis is coincident with the rotation axis of the R joint that connects the 5R PM and the base. Meanwhile, a right-handed coordinate system $N-uvw$ is attached to the MP. The w -axis is normal to the MP, the u -axis is perpendicular to the Z and w axes. A moving coordinate system $O-xyz$ is attached to point O. The x -axis is parallel to the X -axis, and the y -axis is vertical to the plane of the 5R PM.

Fig. 1 Two-axis solar tracker

In Fig. 2(a), the rotation angle of the 5R PM around the X -axis is θ_1 . θ_3 and θ_4 are two rotation angles around two axes of the U joint connecting the 5R PM and the MP. In Fig. 2(b), θ_A , θ_B , θ_C , θ_D and θ_E are the rotation angles of R joints A, B, C, D and E in the 5R PM, respectively. θ_2 is the angle between the y -axis and \overline{CQ} , and denotes another rotation angle in the compound R joint C.

The inverse kinematics of the solar tracker is to determine the actuated angles θ_A and θ_E with the given unit vector \mathbf{w} of the w -axis. The unit vector \mathbf{w} can be described by angles (α, β) as

$$\mathbf{w} = \mathbf{R}_\alpha \mathbf{R}_\beta \mathbf{e}_3 \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{e}_i (i = 1, 2, 3)$ is i -th column of the 3×3 identity matrix,

$$\mathbf{R}_\alpha = \begin{bmatrix} \cos\alpha & -\sin\alpha & 0 \\ \sin\alpha & \cos\alpha & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \text{ and } \mathbf{R}_\beta = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos\beta & -\sin\beta \\ 0 & \sin\beta & \cos\beta \end{bmatrix},$$

α and β represent the rotation angles of two revolute joints in the vertical pole and transversal pole connected to the MP as shown

in Fig. 2(a).

Thus, α and β can be expressed as

$$\alpha = \arctan\left(-\frac{\mathbf{e}_3^T \mathbf{w}}{\mathbf{e}_2^T \mathbf{w}}\right), \beta = \arccos(\mathbf{e}_3^T \mathbf{w}) \quad (2)$$

For the two-axis solar tracker shown in Fig. 2(a), the closed-loop kinematic equations can be written as

$$\mathbf{l}_1 + \mathbf{R}_1 \mathbf{r}_c + \mathbf{R}_1 \mathbf{R}_2 \mathbf{l}_2 = \mathbf{l}_h + \mathbf{R}_\alpha \mathbf{R}_\beta \mathbf{l}_a \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{R}_1 \mathbf{R}_2 \mathbf{R}_3 \mathbf{R}_4 = \mathbf{R}_\alpha \mathbf{R}_\beta \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{R}_i is the orientation matrix about θ_i ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$), $\mathbf{l}_a = [a_x, a_y, a_z]^T$ is the position vector (\overline{SQ}) in the coordinate system $N-uvw$, $\mathbf{r}_c = [x_c, 0, z_c]^T$ is the position of point C in the coordinate system $O-xyz$, $\mathbf{l}_1 = -l_1 \mathbf{e}_2$, $\mathbf{l}_2 = l_2 \mathbf{e}_3$, $\mathbf{l}_h = h \mathbf{e}_3$, l_1 and l_2 are the length of OM and CQ, h is the length of the link MS.

(a) 2-axis solar tracker
Fig. 2 Schematic diagram.

(b) 5R PM

Based on the term of Eq. (3) on y and z axes, θ_1 can be expressed as

$$\theta_1 = \arctan\left(\frac{a_z \cos \alpha \sin \beta - a_x \sin \alpha - a_y \cos \alpha \cos \beta - l_1}{h + a_y \sin \beta + a_z \cos \beta}\right) \quad (5)$$

Based on (4) and (5), θ_2, θ_3 and θ_4 can be determined by $\mathbf{R}_2 \mathbf{R}_3 \mathbf{R}_4 = \mathbf{R}_1^T \mathbf{R}_\alpha \mathbf{R}_\beta$ as

$$\theta_2 = \arctan\left(\frac{\sin \alpha \sin \beta}{\sin \theta_1 \cos \alpha \sin \beta + \cos \theta_1 \cos \beta}\right) \quad (6)$$

$$\theta_3 = \arcsin(\cos \theta_1 \cos \alpha \sin \beta - \sin \theta_1 \cos \beta) \quad (7)$$

$$\theta_4 = \arctan\left(\frac{\cos \theta_1 \sin \alpha}{\cos \theta_1 \cos \alpha \cos \beta + \sin \theta_1 \sin \beta}\right) \quad (8)$$

Based on the terms of (3) on x and z axes, x_c and z_c can be expressed by θ_1 and θ_2 .

$$x_c = a_x \cos \alpha - a_y \sin \alpha \cos \beta + a_z \sin \alpha \sin \beta - l_2 \sin \theta_2 \quad (9)$$

$$z_c = \frac{h + a_y \sin \beta + a_z \cos \beta}{\cos \theta_1} - l_2 \cos \theta_2 \quad (10)$$

For the 5R PM shown in Fig. 2(b), the closed-loop kinematic equations can be written as

$$\mathbf{R}_A \mathbf{R}_B \mathbf{R}_C = \mathbf{R}_E \mathbf{R}_D \quad (11)$$

$$\mathbf{r}_{OA} + \mathbf{R}_A \mathbf{r}_2 + \mathbf{R}_A \mathbf{R}_B \mathbf{r}_3 = \mathbf{r}_{OE} + \mathbf{R}_E \mathbf{r}_5 + \mathbf{R}_E \mathbf{R}_D \mathbf{r}_4 \quad (12)$$

where \mathbf{R}_i is the orientation matrix that rotates about θ_i ($i = A, B, C, D, E$), $\mathbf{r}_{OA} = [-r_1/2, 0, d]^T$, $\mathbf{r}_{OE} = [r_1/2, 0, d]^T$, $\mathbf{r}_2 = -r_2 \mathbf{e}_1$, $\mathbf{r}_3 = -r_3 \mathbf{e}_1$, $\mathbf{r}_4 = r_4 \mathbf{e}_1$, $\mathbf{r}_5 = -r_5 \mathbf{e}_1$, r_1, r_2, r_3, r_4 and r_5 are the length of links EA, AB, BC, CD and DE, and d is the

distance from link EA to point O.

Since both sides of (12) equal \mathbf{r}_c , the terms of (12) on the x and z axes can be rewritten as

$$\begin{bmatrix} -r_3 \cos(\theta_A + \theta_B) - r_2 \cos \theta_A - \frac{r_1}{2} \\ r_3 \sin(\theta_A + \theta_B) + r_2 \sin \theta_A + d \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_c \\ z_c \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} r_4 \cos(\theta_D + \theta_E) - r_5 \cos \theta_E + \frac{r_1}{2} \\ -r_4 \sin(\theta_D + \theta_E) + r_5 \sin \theta_E + d \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_c \\ z_c \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

Based on (13) and (14), $\theta_A, \theta_B, \theta_D$ and θ_E can be obtained as

$$\theta_A = \pi - \arctan\left(\frac{z_c - d}{x_c + \frac{r_1}{2}}\right) - \arccos\left(\frac{L_+ + r_2^2 - r_3^2}{2r_2 \sqrt{L_+}}\right) \quad (15)$$

$$\theta_B = \pi - \arctan\left(\frac{z_c - d - r_2 \sin \theta_A}{x_c + \frac{r_1}{2} + r_2 \cos \theta_A}\right) - \theta_A \quad (16)$$

$$\theta_E = \pi - \arctan\left(\frac{z_c - d}{x_c - \frac{r_1}{2}}\right) - \arccos\left(\frac{L_- + r_5^2 - r_4^2}{2r_5 \sqrt{L_-}}\right) \quad (17)$$

$$\theta_D = \pi - \arctan\left(\frac{z_c - d - r_5 \sin \theta_E}{x_c - \frac{r_1}{2} + r_5 \cos \theta_E}\right) - \theta_E \quad (18)$$

where $L_+ = (z_c - d)^2 + (x_c + r_1/2)^2$ and $L_- = (z_c - d)^2 + (x_c - r_1/2)^2$. Based on (11), θ_C can be expressed as

$$\theta_C = \theta_D + \theta_E - \theta_A - \theta_B \quad (19)$$

Thus, when the unit vector of w axis, \mathbf{w} is given, the rotational angles of all revolute joints in the two-axis solar tracker can be determined by (2), (5)-(8) and (15)-(19).

III. ERROR MODELING

Three basic requirements in the error model can be defined as: (a) completeness - enough parameters to describe any possible geometric errors which affect the MP; (b) continuity - infinitesimal changes in the geometric structure result in infinitesimal values for the errors; (c) minimality - no redundant errors [21].

Compared with a great deal of research on error modeling of the serial robot with only actuated joints, the error modeling of the over-constrained PM has some differences based on these three requirements:

(a) completeness - there are passive errors, which are the motion errors in passive joints and change with other geometric errors and the pose of the PM;

(b) continuity - due to the overdetermined problem caused by the over-constrained structure, any passive error may not satisfy the closed-loop error equations which would destroy the continuity and rationality of the error model, therefore constraints among geometric errors must exist;

(c) minimality - the correlation of geometric errors in PM is not intuitive due to (a) and (b).

To make the error model strictly satisfy the above requirements, a new error modeling method for the over-constrained PM is proposed. The error modeling method is derived by eliminating passive errors and determining the constraints among geometric errors. Based on the algebraic approach, the existence and the specific expression of the error

constraint equations are strictly deduced. In addition, the redundant errors are eliminated by the geometric error reconstruction in the closed-loop error equations.

The error modeling of the proposed 2-axis solar tracker can be divided into two steps: 1) the error model of the 5R PM is formulated by considering the constraints among geometric errors and passive errors; 2) the error model of the whole solar tracker is derived based on the 5R PM model. Finally, the minimality of the error model is validated.

A. 5R planar PM error model

The perturbation theory finds a solution by breaking the problem into “solvable” and “perturbative” parts, and only the first-order perturbation correction is usually retained in the solution [16]. In the robot kinematics with geometric errors, the nominal geometrical parameters and the joint angles determined by the actuators and the nominal kinematics can be regarded as the solvable part, while the geometric errors can be viewed as perturbation terms of its geometric parameters [31]. Specifically, by the perturbation of the orientation matrix and the position vector, 3 orientation errors and 3 position errors can be obtained, respectively. For the completeness of the error model, the error of the parameter with the ideal zero value is also considered in the model. For example, the position errors between the two rotation axes in a U joint are considered.

The nominal closed-loop kinematic equations of the 5R PM can be divided into orientation and position closed-loop equations in (11) and (12). Thus, the error model of the 5R PM can be established through the perturbation of (11) and (12). First, taking perturbation of (11) and then multiply $\mathbf{R}_C^T \mathbf{R}_B^T \mathbf{R}_A^T$ on both sides leads to

$$\widehat{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_A + \mathbf{R}_A \widehat{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_B \mathbf{R}_A^T + \mathbf{R}_A \mathbf{R}_B \widehat{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_C \mathbf{R}_B^T \mathbf{R}_A^T = \widehat{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_E + \mathbf{R}_E \widehat{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_D \mathbf{R}_E^T \quad (20)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\omega}_i$ is the orientation errors in \mathbf{R}_i ($i = A, B, C, D, E$), and

$$\widehat{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_i = (\boldsymbol{\omega}_i)^\wedge = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -\omega_{iz} & \omega_{iy} \\ \omega_{iz} & 0 & -\omega_{ix} \\ -\omega_{iy} & \omega_{ix} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \text{ represents the screw}$$

matrix of $\boldsymbol{\omega}_i = [\omega_{ix}, \omega_{iy}, \omega_{iz}]^T$. According to the identity

$$(\mathbf{R}\boldsymbol{\omega})^\wedge = \mathbf{R}\widehat{\boldsymbol{\omega}}\mathbf{R}^T, \quad (20) \text{ can be written as}$$

$$\boldsymbol{\omega}_A + \mathbf{R}_A \boldsymbol{\omega}_B + \mathbf{R}_A \mathbf{R}_B \boldsymbol{\omega}_C = \boldsymbol{\omega}_E + \mathbf{R}_E \boldsymbol{\omega}_D \quad (21)$$

where ω_{By} , ω_{Cy} and ω_{Dy} are passive errors. The projection of Eq. (21) on x and z axes can be expressed as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \omega_{Ax} \\ \omega_{Az} \end{bmatrix} + \mathbf{T}_A \begin{bmatrix} \omega_{Bx} \\ \omega_{Bz} \end{bmatrix} + \mathbf{T}_{A+B} \begin{bmatrix} \omega_{Cx} \\ \omega_{Cz} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \omega_{Ex} \\ \omega_{Ez} \end{bmatrix} + \mathbf{T}_E \begin{bmatrix} \omega_{Dx} \\ \omega_{Dz} \end{bmatrix} \quad (22)$$

where $\theta_{i+j} = \theta_i + \theta_j$, $\mathbf{T}_i = \begin{bmatrix} \cos\theta_i & \sin\theta_i \\ -\sin\theta_i & \cos\theta_i \end{bmatrix}$.

Based on (13) and (14), the relationship among θ_A , θ_B and θ_E can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} & (r_3 \cos\theta_{A+B} + r_2 \cos\theta_A - r_5 \cos\theta_E)^2 \\ & + (r_3 \sin\theta_{A+B} + r_2 \sin\theta_A - r_5 \sin\theta_E)^2 = r_4^2 \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

For any $\{\theta_A, \theta_B, \theta_E\}$ in (23), (22) should be satisfied. Since there are two DOFs with the actuated angles θ_A and θ_E in the 5R PM, θ_B can be determined by θ_A and θ_E . When θ_B is viewed as a function of θ_A and θ_E in (23), taking a partial derivative of θ_B to θ_A and θ_E leads to

$$\frac{\partial \theta_B}{\partial \theta_E} = -\frac{\partial \theta_B}{\partial \theta_A} = \frac{r_2 r_5 \sin\theta_{A-E} + r_3 r_5 \sin\theta_{A+B-E}}{-r_2 r_3 \sin\theta_B + r_3 r_5 \sin\theta_{A+B-E}} \quad (24)$$

Based on (15)-(17) and (24), $\frac{\partial \theta_B}{\partial \theta_E} = -\frac{\partial \theta_B}{\partial \theta_A}$ is not identically equal to 0 or 1. Similarly, when θ_B is viewed as a function of θ_A and θ_E in (22), taking the mixed second-order partial derivative with respect to θ_A and θ_E yields

$$\mathbf{K} \begin{bmatrix} \omega_{Cx} \\ \omega_{Cz} \end{bmatrix} = 0 \quad (25)$$

where $\mathbf{K} = \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{T}_{A+B}}{\partial \theta_A \partial \theta_E} = -\left(1 + \frac{\partial \theta_B}{\partial \theta_A}\right) \frac{\partial \theta_B}{\partial \theta_E} \mathbf{T}_{A+B} + \frac{\partial^2 \theta_B}{\partial \theta_A \partial \theta_E} \bar{\mathbf{T}}_{A+B}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{T}}_i = \partial \mathbf{T}_i / \partial \theta_i = \begin{bmatrix} -\sin\theta_i & \cos\theta_i \\ -\cos\theta_i & -\sin\theta_i \end{bmatrix}$. The determinant of \mathbf{K} can be simplified as

$$|\mathbf{K}| = \left(\frac{\partial \theta_B}{\partial \theta_E} \left(1 - \frac{\partial \theta_B}{\partial \theta_E}\right)\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial^2 \theta_B}{\partial \theta_A \partial \theta_E}\right)^2 > 0 \quad (26)$$

Since \mathbf{K} is nonsingular, both ω_{Cx} and ω_{Cz} are zero. Further, taking a partial derivative of (22) to θ_A leads to

$$\begin{bmatrix} -\sin\theta_A & \cos\theta_A \\ -\cos\theta_A & -\sin\theta_A \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \omega_{Bx} \\ \omega_{Bz} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{0} \quad (27)$$

Since the matrix on the left of (27) is always invertible, both ω_{Bx} and ω_{Bz} are zero. Similarly, taking the partial derivative of (22) with respect to θ_D results in $\omega_{Dx} = \omega_{Dz} = 0$. Thus, the constraint equations among the orientation errors on x and z axes can be summarized in

$$\begin{bmatrix} \omega_{Ax} \\ \omega_{Az} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \omega_{Ex} \\ \omega_{Ez} \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} \omega_{Bx} \\ \omega_{Bz} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \omega_{Cx} \\ \omega_{Cz} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \omega_{Dx} \\ \omega_{Dz} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (28)$$

Since ω_{Ax} and ω_{Az} can be regarded as orientation assembly errors of the 5R PM in the solar tracker which would be considered in Section IIIB, ω_{Ax} and ω_{Az} can be viewed as redundant in the error model. Then, taking perturbation on (12), and the closed-loop error equations can be obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} & \delta \mathbf{r}_{0A} + \mathbf{R}_A \delta \mathbf{r}_2 + \mathbf{R}_A \mathbf{R}_B \delta \mathbf{r}_3 + \widehat{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_A (\mathbf{R}_A \mathbf{r}_2 + \mathbf{R}_A \mathbf{R}_B \mathbf{r}_3) \\ & + \mathbf{R}_A \widehat{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_B \mathbf{R}_B \mathbf{r}_3 = \delta \mathbf{r}_{0E} + \mathbf{R}_E \delta \mathbf{r}_5 + \mathbf{R}_E \mathbf{R}_D \delta \mathbf{r}_4 \\ & + \widehat{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_E (\mathbf{R}_E \mathbf{r}_5 + \mathbf{R}_E \mathbf{R}_D \mathbf{r}_4) + \mathbf{R}_E \widehat{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_D \mathbf{R}_D \mathbf{r}_4 \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

where $\delta \mathbf{r}_* = [\delta r_{*x}, \delta r_{*y}, \delta r_{*z}]^T$ is the position errors of $\mathbf{r}_* \in \{\mathbf{r}_{0A}, \mathbf{r}_{0E}, \mathbf{r}_2, \mathbf{r}_3, \mathbf{r}_4, \mathbf{r}_5\}$.

Based on (28) and (29), the constraint equation among the position errors on y axis can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} & \delta r_{0Ay} + \omega_{Az} \frac{r_1}{2} + \delta r_{2y} + \delta r_{3y} = \\ & \delta r_{0Ey} - \omega_{Ez} \frac{r_1}{2} + \delta r_{4y} + \delta r_{5y} \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

Similarly, since both sides of (30) can be regarded as position assembly errors of the 5R PM in the solar tracker, they can be viewed as redundant here and be considered in Section IIIB.

Thus, the constraint equations among geometric errors in the 5R PM can be expressed as (28) and (30) based on the above strict algebraic derivation. It should be noted that the reason why the constraints must exist is that the number of the closed-loop error equations in (21) and (29) is larger than that of passive errors. Due to the similarity of over-constrained PMs at this point, the constraints among geometric errors may also exist in other over-constrained PMs, and the method proposed in this article is a useful guideline for them.

Although the error model and error constraints have been determined, there are redundant errors that need to be eliminated. It is noted that when the closed-loop error equations can be reconstructed into an equivalent equation with fewer

elements through the linear combination of geometric errors, the fewer elements can be used to replace the original errors while other elements can be regarded as redundant. For instance, when the error $\delta' = \delta_0 + \delta_1$ can replace δ_0 and δ_1 equivalently in the error equations, then one of δ_0 and δ_1 can be deleted and regarded as the redundant error.

Specially, Since the idle motion would be produced to adapt to the closed-loop error equations for a passive joint, the passive errors can be used to replace any errors' linear combination, while other errors can only be used to replace the errors' combination which does not change with the robot configuration. Thus, the redundant errors can be analytically determined and eliminated.

Based on the error constraint equations, the closed-loop error equations in (21) and (29) can be reconstructed as

$$\begin{aligned} \omega_{By} + \omega_{Cy} &= \omega_{Dy} & (31) \\ \begin{bmatrix} \delta r_{0Ax} \\ \delta r_{0Az} \end{bmatrix} + T_A \begin{bmatrix} \delta r_{2x} \\ \delta r_{2z} \end{bmatrix} + T_{A+B} \begin{bmatrix} \delta r_{3x} \\ \omega_{By} r_3 \end{bmatrix} \\ &= T_E \begin{bmatrix} \delta r_{5x} \\ \delta r_{5z} \end{bmatrix} + T_{D+E} \begin{bmatrix} \delta r_{4x} \\ -\omega_{Dy} r_4 \end{bmatrix} & (32) \end{aligned}$$

where the reconstruction way can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \delta r_{0Ax} &\leftarrow \delta r_{0Ax} - \delta r_{0Ex}, \delta r_{0Az} \leftarrow \delta r_{0Az} - \delta r_{0Ez} \\ \delta r_{2z} &\leftarrow \delta r_{2z} + \omega_{Ay} r_2, \omega_{By} \leftarrow \omega_{By} + \omega_{Ay} + \frac{\delta r_{3z}}{r_3} \\ \delta r_{5z} &\leftarrow \delta r_{5z} + \omega_{Ey} r_5, \omega_{Cy} \leftarrow \omega_{Cy} - \frac{\delta r_{4z}}{r_4} - \frac{\delta r_{3z}}{r_3} \\ \omega_{Dy} &\leftarrow \omega_{Dy} + \omega_{Ey} - \frac{\delta r_{4z}}{r_4} & (33) \end{aligned}$$

The original error model in (21) and (29) can be restored by replacing the error on the arrow's left side with the error expression on the right side in the reconstructed error model in (31) and (32). Therefore, compared with the original error model including 33 geometric errors, the reconstructed error model without redundant errors only includes 11 errors, where the passive errors $\{\omega_{By}, \omega_{Cy}, \omega_{Dy}\}$ can be eliminated by the linear combination of other 8 errors based on (31) and (32). Then, the pose errors of the 5R PM in the coordinate system O - xyz , ω_{co} and δr_{co} can be obtained by the left or right sides of (31) and (32).

Thus, the error model without redundant errors is established. Similar to the previous error models [13], the error model contains two implicit assumptions: no deformation and no joint clearance. since the actual geometric error does not perfectly satisfy the constraints, the derivation of constraints in the method is helpful to guide future research in the over-constrained PM to abandon these two assumptions.

B. Solar tracker error Model

As shown in Fig. 2, the 5R PM is a part of the two-axis solar tracker. Therefore, the assembly errors of the 5R PM, $\{\omega_{as}, \delta r_{as}\}$, should be considered in the error model of the whole solar tracker. Thus, the pose errors of the 5R PM can be expressed as $\{\omega_c, \delta r_c\}$ where $\omega_c = \omega_{co} + \omega_{as}$ and $\delta r_c = \delta r_{co} + \delta r_{as} + \hat{\omega}_{as} r_c$. Thus, the perturbation on (3) and (4) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \delta l_1 + R_1 \delta r_c + R_1 R_2 \delta l_2 + R_1 R_2 R_3 \delta l_3 + \\ \hat{\omega}_1 (R_1 r_c + R_1 R_2 l_2) + R_1 (\hat{\omega}_2 + \hat{\omega}_c) R_2 l_2 = \delta l_h + \\ R_\alpha \delta l_\alpha + R_\alpha R_\beta \delta l_\alpha + \hat{\omega}_\alpha R_\alpha R_\beta l_\alpha + R_\alpha \hat{\omega}_\beta R_\beta l_\alpha & (34) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \omega_1 + R_1 (\omega_c + \omega_2) + R_1 R_2 \omega_3 + \\ R_1 R_2 R_3 \omega_4 = \omega_\alpha + R_\alpha \omega_\beta & (35) \end{aligned}$$

where δl_* is the position errors of l_* in $\{l_1, l_2, l_h, l_\alpha, l_\beta\}$, ω_* is the orientation errors in R_* in $\{R_1, R_2, R_3, R_4, R_\alpha, R_\beta\}$, $l_\alpha = \mathbf{0}$ denotes the position vector between α and β rotation axes in the U joint.

Similarly, the closed-loop error equations in (34) and (35) can be reconstructed by the following substitution.

$$\begin{aligned} \omega_1 &\leftarrow [\omega_{1x} + \omega_{asx} - \omega_{\alpha x}, 0, \omega_{1z} + \omega_{asz}]^T \\ \omega_2 &\leftarrow \omega_2 + (\omega_{asy} + \omega_{Dy} + \omega_{3y}) e_2 \\ \omega_3 &\leftarrow [\omega_{3x} + \omega_{4x}, 0, \omega_{3z}]^T, \omega_4 \leftarrow [0, \omega_{4y}, \omega_{4z}]^T \\ \omega_\alpha &\leftarrow \omega_\alpha - \omega_{1y} e_2 - (\omega_{1z} - \omega_{\beta z}) e_3 \\ \omega_\beta &\leftarrow [\omega_{\beta x}, \omega_{\beta y}, 0]^T, \omega_{as} \leftarrow \mathbf{0} \\ \delta l_h &\leftarrow \delta l_h - \delta l_1 + (\hat{l}_1 - \hat{l}_h) [\omega_{\alpha x}, -\omega_{1y}, 0]^T + \\ & \quad (l_h - l_1 - \frac{r_1}{2} e_1) \bar{\delta} l_{2z} + [-\delta r_{asx}, 0, \delta l_{\alpha z}]^T & (36) \end{aligned}$$

$$\delta l_\alpha \leftarrow \delta l_{\alpha y} e_2, \delta l_3 \leftarrow [\delta l_{3x} + \delta l_{2x} - \omega_{3y} l_2, \delta l_{3y}, 0]^T$$

$$\delta l_\alpha \leftarrow \delta l_\alpha + \delta l_{\alpha x} e_1 - \delta l_{3z} e_3 + \bar{\delta} l_{2z} l_\alpha$$

$$\delta r_{as} \leftarrow [0, \delta r_{asy} + \delta l_{2y}, \delta r_{asz} + \bar{\delta} l_{2z} d]^T$$

$$\delta r_{0Ax} \leftarrow \delta r_{0Ax} + r_1 \bar{\delta} l_{2z}, \delta r_{4x} \leftarrow \delta r_{4x} - r_4 \bar{\delta} l_{2z}$$

$$\delta r_{ix} \leftarrow \delta r_{ix} + r_i \bar{\delta} l_{2z}, i = 2, 3, 5$$

where $\bar{\delta} l_{2z} = \delta l_{2z} / l_2$. Based on (36), the redundant errors in (34) and (35) can be determined as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \omega_{as}, \omega_{1y}, \omega_{1z}, \omega_{3y}, \omega_{4x}, \omega_{\alpha x}, \omega_{\beta z}, \\ \delta r_{asx}, \delta l_1, \delta l_2, \delta l_{3z}, \delta l_{\alpha x}, \delta l_{\alpha z} \end{bmatrix} & (37)$$

Thus, the reconstructed error model can be expressed as

$$M_L \delta p_{pa} = M_R \delta p_{ot} & (38)$$

where $\delta p_{pa} \in \mathbb{R}^6$ denotes all passive errors, $\delta p_{ot} \in \mathbb{R}^{26}$ denotes other independent geometric errors, are coefficient matrices determined by (34)-(36).

$$\delta p_{pa}^T = [\omega_{1x}, \omega_{2y}, \omega_{3x}, \omega_{4z}, \omega_{\alpha z}, \omega_{\beta x}]$$

$$\delta p_{ot}^T = \begin{bmatrix} \delta r_{0Ax}, \delta r_{0Az}, \delta r_{2x}, \delta r_{2z}, \delta r_{3x}, \delta r_{4x}, \\ \delta r_{5x}, \delta r_{5z}, \omega_{1z}, \omega_{2x}, \omega_{2z}, \omega_{3z}, \omega_{4y}, \omega_{\alpha y}, \\ \omega_{\beta y}, \delta l_h^T, \delta l_\alpha^T, \delta l_{asy}, \delta l_{asz}, \delta l_{3x}, \delta l_{3y}, \delta l_{\alpha y} \end{bmatrix} & (39)$$

Since the number of the closed-loop error equations in (38) is equal to that of passive errors, there is no constraint among geometric errors and $\delta p_{pa} = M_L^{-1} M_R \delta p_{ot}$. Then, define the orientation errors ω_{mp} as the left or right side of (34), which can be written as $M_{mp} \delta p_{ot}$. Thus, the orientation errors of the solar tracker in the coordinate system M - XYZ can be expressed as

$$\omega = \omega_{mp} + \omega_b = [M_{mp}, I_3] \delta p & (40)$$

where I_3 is the identity matrix, $\delta p = [\delta p_{ot}^T, \omega_b^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{29}$ denotes all independent errors in the solar tracker. Since only two orientation errors need to be measured and compensated in the two-axis solar tracker, the output errors in (40) should be rewritten as the w -axis errors δw .

$$\delta w = \delta (R_\alpha R_\beta e_3) = \hat{\omega} w = -\hat{w} \omega = M \delta p & (41)$$

where $M = -\hat{w} [M_{mp}, I_3]$ is the error mapping matrix

(EMM). Thus, the solar tracker error model is established.

C. Model-minimality validation

The completeness and continuity of the model can be ensured due to the perturbation method and the constraint equations. However, the minimality still can not be ensured since it is not sure that all redundant errors are eliminated.

According to the definition of minimality, the geometric errors are independent of each other, which means that the corresponding identification matrix is column full rank. Thus, the minimality can be validated by the process: select randomly k configurations of the solar tracker and then determine whether the convergence rank(T_k) is equal to the number of errors with the increase of k , where T_k is defined as

$$T_k = [M_1^T, \dots, M_k^T]^T \quad (42)$$

and M_i is the EMM of the i -th selected configuration.

Based on the nominal geometric parameters in Table I, rank(T_k) converges to 29 which is the number of elements in δp , as shown in Fig. 3. Therefore, the error model in (41) is minimal.

TABLE I

Geometrical Parameters of 2-Axis Solar Tracker (mm)

a_x	0	d	105
a_y	-200	r_1	400
a_z	-8	r_2	520
l_1	480	r_3	800
h	960	r_4	800
l_2	85	r_5	520

Fig. 3 Rank(T_k) and difference of rank(T_k).

IV. PARAMETER IDENTIFICATION

A. Iterative Tikhonov regularization method

For a specified configuration of the solar tracker, w axis error δw can be obtained by $M\delta p$ based on (41). By measuring w axis error δw_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$) under n different configurations, the identification equations can be written as

$$\delta w_t = M_t \delta p \quad (43)$$

where $\delta w_t = [\delta w_1^T, \dots, \delta w_n^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{3n}$, $M_t = [M_1^T, \dots, M_n^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{3n \times 29}$, M_i is the EMM of i -th configuration. Based on Fig. 3, each configuration can provide 2 independent identification equations and at least 15 configurations are required to ensure that M_t is column full rank. Based on (43), The LS solution can be expressed as

$$\delta p = (M_t^T M_t)^{-1} M_t^T \delta w_t \quad (44)$$

However, the amplification of the small singular value of M_t on the noise in δw_t leads to a large identification variance. Thus, the standard Tikhonov regularization method is generally

used to find the smooth solution to the ill-posed problem and can be written as

$$\delta p = (M_t^T M_t + \lambda I)^{-1} M_t^T \delta w_t \quad (45)$$

where λ is the regularization parameter and is a small positive number, I is the identity matrix. Taking compact SVD on M_t leads to

$M_t = U_t \Sigma_t V_t^T$, $\Sigma_t = \text{diag}([\dots, \sigma_i, \dots])$, $i = 1, \dots, 29$ (46) where the column vectors of $U_t \in \mathbb{R}^{3n \times 29}$ are orthogonal, $\Sigma_t \in \mathbb{R}^{29 \times 29}$ is a diagonal matrix, $V_t \in \mathbb{R}^{29 \times 29}$ is an orthogonal matrix, σ_i is the singular value of M_t , and $\text{diag}(x)$ represents the diagonal matrix with x as the diagonal elements

Based on (45) and (46), δp can be rewritten as

$$\delta p = V_t \Sigma_\lambda^{-1} U_t^T \delta w_t, \Sigma_\lambda = \text{diag} \left(\left[\dots, \sigma_i + \frac{\lambda}{\sigma_i}, \dots \right] \right) \quad (47)$$

Based on (46) and (47), one may see that the difference between the LS method and the standard Tikhonov method is diagonal matrices Σ_t and Σ_λ . Based on the regularization parameter λ , Σ_t is replaced with Σ_λ in δp by adding positive elements to the diagonals. In general, the Tikhonov regularization method provides the improved efficiency in parameter identification in exchange for a tolerable amount of bias. As the regularization parameter λ decreases and approaches 0, the bias of the estimated parameters would decrease and the result approaches the LS solution, while the variance of the estimated parameters would increase and the result is easily affected by noise.

However, the parameter λ cannot be theoretically obtained. The traditional Tikhonov regularization methods are susceptible to random measurement noise since it is the posterior method based on λ obtained by the measurement data in kinematic calibration. In addition, the regularization parameter obtained by these traditional methods, for instance the L-curve method and GCV method, has no clear physical meaning but only statistical significance. Thus, the prior regularization identification method with clear physical meaning is valuable for kinematic calibration. In this paper, an iterative Tikhonov regularization method (IterTik) is proposed as

$\delta p_{k+1} = \delta p_k + (M_t^T M_t + \lambda I)^{-1} M_t^T (\delta w_t - M_t \delta p_k)$ (48) where the initial value δp_0 is set to $\mathbf{0}$ since geometric errors are generally considered as zero mean distributions.

Hanke et al[32] and Buccini et al[33] presented Iterated Tikhonov regularization methods similar to equation (48) and their methods have statistically advantages over traditional Tikhonov regularization method. However, in their research, the selection method of regularization parameter λ is investigated, while there has less discussion on the termination conditions of iterations.

In the kinematic calibration of robots, due to the ill-posed problem of the identification matrix, more attention is paid to the numerical stability of the error identification result δp to avoid big error at the pose within the workspace that is different from the measurement points. Thus, the traditional regularization methods, represented by L-curves and GCVs, still are the main solutions for parameter identification. In order to fully utilize the good performance of iterative regularization

methods in robot calibration, this paper focuses more on the termination conditions of the iterative methods which can be expressed as

$$\|\delta\mathbf{w}_t - \mathbf{M}_t\delta\mathbf{p}_k\|_\infty < \gamma_{noise} \quad (49)$$

where $\|\delta\mathbf{w}_t - \mathbf{M}_t\delta\mathbf{p}_k\|_\infty$ is the maximum absolute value of the residual error, and γ_{noise} is the amplitude of measurement noise. γ_{noise} can be determined with prior knowledge, for instance repeated measurement data and system analysis. Under a fixed pose of the robot, the measurement system can repeatedly measure the related data. Each measurement data is different due to the noise, and the inconsistency of their data can be regarded as the amplitude of noise.

Since γ_{noise} represents a physical variable, the iterative termination criterion has a physical meaning.

Based on SVD decomposition, $\mathbf{I} - (\mathbf{M}_t^T\mathbf{M}_t + \lambda\mathbf{I})^{-1}\mathbf{M}_t^T\mathbf{M}_t = \mathbf{V}_t\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\sigma\mathbf{V}_t^T$, where $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\sigma = \text{diag}\left(\left[\dots, \frac{\lambda}{\sigma_i^2 + \lambda}, \dots\right]\right)$ is a diagonal matrix. Then, based on (46), (48) can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} & \delta\mathbf{p}_{k+1} - \mathbf{V}_t\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\sigma^{-1}\mathbf{U}_t^T\delta\mathbf{w}_t \\ = & \mathbf{V}_t\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\sigma\mathbf{V}_t^T\delta\mathbf{p}_k + ((\mathbf{M}_t^T\mathbf{M}_t + \lambda\mathbf{I})^{-1}\mathbf{M}_t^T - \mathbf{V}_t\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\sigma^{-1}\mathbf{U}_t^T)\delta\mathbf{w}_t \\ = & \mathbf{V}_t\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\sigma\mathbf{V}_t^T(\delta\mathbf{p}_k - \mathbf{V}_t\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\sigma^{-1}\mathbf{U}_t^T\delta\mathbf{w}_t) \end{aligned} \quad (50)$$

where $\mathbf{V}_t\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\sigma^{-1}\mathbf{U}_t^T - (\mathbf{M}_t^T\mathbf{M}_t + \lambda\mathbf{I})^{-1}\mathbf{M}_t^T = (\mathbf{I} - (\mathbf{M}_t^T\mathbf{M}_t + \lambda\mathbf{I})^{-1}\mathbf{M}_t^T\mathbf{M}_t)\mathbf{V}_t\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\sigma^{-1}\mathbf{U}_t^T = \mathbf{V}_t\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\sigma\mathbf{V}_t^T\mathbf{V}_t\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\sigma^{-1}\mathbf{U}_t^T$. Thus, Eq. (51) can be expressed as

$$\delta\mathbf{p}_k = \mathbf{V}_t(\mathbf{I} - \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\sigma^k)\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\sigma^{-1}\mathbf{U}_t^T\delta\mathbf{w}_t \quad (51)$$

Note that all element values of $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\sigma$ are smaller than 1. It means that the iterative value converges quickly on the geometric error sensitive to the error of the MP and slowly on the other geometric error.

When k approaches infinity, $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\sigma^k$ approaches the 0 matrix. The error identification result $\delta\mathbf{p}$ is completely consistent with the results obtained by the LS method, and the residual error $\delta\mathbf{w}_t - \mathbf{M}_t\delta\mathbf{p}_k$ get its minimum value. But, it does not mean that this is a high-precision identification result since the LS method maybe amplify the identification bias of some insensitive geometric errors, resulting in poor prediction accuracy at non-measurement points. Compared to traditional LS method, based on (49), the iterative process in the proposed method is reasonably terminated that can avoid the amplification of identification bias. Although the residual error can not get its minimum value, the stability of robot calibration is improved.

Compared with the regularization parameters in the traditional Tikhonov method, the number of iterations in the proposed method has a clearer physical meaning which is to suppress the identification variance on the insensitive geometric error and maintain the identification accuracy of the sensitive geometric error.

B. Comparison of the proposed method and others

In the Tikhonov regularization method, the regularization parameter is generally determined based on the L-curve method and GCV method. Here, the IterTik method is compared with the LS method and these two regularization methods by the error identification simulation in the kinematic calibration of the solar tracker. The simulation is summarized in five steps:

1) Measurement and validation configurations are selected. The measurement configurations are utilized to identify geometric errors while validation configurations are used to validate the accuracy with identified errors. For the reliability of simulations, both the distribution range and the number of validation configurations should be larger than that of measurement configurations. Specifically, 5×5 measurement configurations are uniformly selected in $\{\alpha \in [-40, 40] \text{deg}, \beta \in [-46, 14] \text{deg}\}$, while 41×41 validation configurations are randomly selected in $\{\alpha \in [-50, 50] \text{deg}, \beta \in [-60, 20] \text{deg}\}$.

2) A group of parameters is randomly set as the true geometric errors to be identified, where every position (orientation) error conforms to a normal distribution with zero mean and standard deviation of 1 mm and 0.25 deg.

3) The measurement noise is inevitable and should be considered in the simulation. Considering the effect of noise intensity on the identification method, uniformly distributed noises with different amplitudes are used for the simulation.

4) Geometric errors are identified based on the simulated measurement data and the identification method. To validate the effectiveness and advantages of the IterTik method proposed in this paper, the LS method, L-curve method and GCV method are used for comparison.

5) Based on the identified errors in Step 4 and the given true errors in Step 1, the error compensation is simulated at the validation pose. The maximum errors along the directions α and β after the error compensation in the 41×41 validation configurations are regarded as the compensation residual and used to evaluate the accuracy of identification.

Based on the above steps in the simulation, the compensation residual based on different identification methods under the same noise can be obtained for each simulation. Due to the randomness of the single simulation, it is necessary to simulate many times to obtain enough compensation residuals to evaluate the reliability of the identification method.

It is assumed that the measurement noise obeys the uniform distribution $U(-0.02, 0.02) \text{deg}$ in both directions α and β , the simulation is repeated 1000 times for each identification method. The distributions of the compensation residual under different identification methods are shown in Fig. 4. It can be found that LS method is sensitive to measurement noise. Although L-curve method and GCV method have better identification stability and accuracy than LS method, but they are worse than the method proposed in this paper.

To further compare the IterTik method proposed in this paper with other methods, different measurement noise amplitudes are used in the simulations, and each noise amplitude would be used for 5000 simulations. Similarly, for each simulation, four methods are used for identification, respectively. The results are shown in Fig. 5 and can be concluded that:

1) If the measurement noise is zero, LS method has no compensation residual due to the unbiasedness, and IterTik method is better than the other two regularization methods.

2) Compared with the other three regularization methods, LS method is most sensitive to measurement noise, which shows that regularization method has good noise immunity.

3) Among the three regularization methods, for the different simulated noise amplitudes, the compensation residual

determined by the IterTik method are better than L-curve method and GCV method, especially in the direction β .

Fig. 4 Compensation residual with noise $\sim U(-0.02, 0.02)$ deg.

Fig. 5 Compensation residual with different noises.

Therefore, compared with the LS method, L-curve method and GCV method, the IterTik method proposed in this paper has the best effect on the compensation residual of the solar tracker.

V. ERROR COMPENSATION

Error compensation can be generally implemented by modifying the kinematic or the displacements of actuated joints.

Let \mathbf{q} , \mathbf{f} and \mathbf{f}^{-1} be the displacements of actuated joints, forward kinematics and inverse kinematics. \mathbf{f} is the nonlinear function in terms of the geometric parameters \mathbf{p} and the displacements of actuated joints \mathbf{q} .

$$\mathbf{w} = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}), \quad \mathbf{q} = \mathbf{f}^{-1}(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{w}) \quad (52)$$

For the error $\delta\mathbf{p}$ of the real system, the error compensation is to find the compensation displacements of actuated joints $\delta\mathbf{q}$ to satisfy

$$\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{p} + \delta\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q} + \delta\mathbf{q}) = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}) = \mathbf{w} \quad (53)$$

If the kinematic equations in (53) has the closed-form solution, the compensation value $\delta\mathbf{q}$ can be expressed as

$$\delta\mathbf{q} = \mathbf{f}^{-1}(\mathbf{p} + \delta\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{w}) - \mathbf{f}^{-1}(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{w}) \quad (54)$$

and the error compensation can be implemented by directly modifying the inverse kinematics. However, in general, the inverse kinematics with errors is difficult to be solved analytically. Thus, in this paper, the displacements of actuated joints are changed to compensate for the geometric errors. Based on (53), $\delta\tilde{\mathbf{w}} = \mathbf{w} - \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q} + \delta\mathbf{q})$ can be expressed as

$$\delta\tilde{\mathbf{w}} = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{p} + \delta\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q} + \delta\mathbf{q}) - \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q} + \delta\mathbf{q}) \quad (55)$$

Replacing \mathbf{q} with $\mathbf{q} + \delta\mathbf{q}$ in the proposed error model $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{p} + \delta\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}) - \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}) = \mathbf{M}(\mathbf{w})\delta\mathbf{p}$, $\delta\tilde{\mathbf{w}}$ can be written as

$$\delta\tilde{\mathbf{w}} = \mathbf{M}(\mathbf{w} - \delta\tilde{\mathbf{w}})\delta\mathbf{p} \quad (56)$$

In traditional method, the high-order error item is neglected in the real kinematic model and $\delta\tilde{\mathbf{w}}$ can be simplified as

$$\delta\tilde{\mathbf{w}} = \mathbf{M}(\mathbf{w})\delta\mathbf{p} \quad (57)$$

However, due to error accumulation, the pose errors of the MP may be large even if every geometric error is small. Thus, the high-order error item should be considered in compensation. It means that (56) cannot be simplified as (57), although for a specific \mathbf{w} , the error of the MP still can be accurately estimated by $\mathbf{M}(\mathbf{w})\delta\mathbf{p}$ based on the model-measure-identification-model fitting method. In this paper, an iterative error compensation method is proposed as

$$\delta\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_{i+1} = \mathbf{M}(\mathbf{w} - \delta\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_i)\delta\mathbf{p} \quad (58)$$

The iterative initial value $\delta\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_0$ is zero. When $\delta\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_i$ converges, the iterative computation stops and the convergence value is noted as $\delta\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_\infty$. According to the definition of convergence, $\delta\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_\infty = \mathbf{M}(\mathbf{w} - \delta\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_\infty)\delta\mathbf{p}$. Thus, $\delta\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_\infty$ is the solution of (56) and must be $\delta\tilde{\mathbf{w}}$. Based on the definition of $\delta\tilde{\mathbf{w}}$, the compensation value $\delta\mathbf{q}$ can be written as

$$\delta\mathbf{q} = \mathbf{f}^{-1}(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{w} - \delta\tilde{\mathbf{w}}_\infty) - \mathbf{q} \quad (59)$$

Since the high-order error term is not ignored in the iterative compensation method, kinematic calibration is not affected by the error compensation, but only by the prediction residual of the error model and the measurement noise.

VI. KINEMATIC CALIBRATION

The prototype of the two-axis solar tracker is shown in Fig. 6. The kinematic calibration experiment is carried out on the prototype, as shown in Fig. 7. The experiment of the kinematic calibration is summarized as follows:

- 1) Select measurement configuration. Before the kinematic calibration, measure the w axis and compare the measured \mathbf{w} and the expected \mathbf{w} to obtain $\delta\mathbf{w}_t$.
- 2) The EMM \mathbf{M}_t is determined by the error model, and $\delta\mathbf{p}$ is obtained by the IterTik method.

3) Compensate the orientation errors of the w -axis by the iterative error compensation method. The w -axis errors in measurement configurations after calibration are measured and compared with that before calibration.

4) Select validation configurations. Compensate the orientation errors by δp obtained in Step 2. The w -axis errors before and after calibration in validation configurations are measured.

Since the laser from the laser tracker would be blocked by the big solar mirror, the solar mirror should be removed in the calibration experiment. It is reasonable since the deformation caused by the load is not within the scope of kinematic calibration. In addition, since the top plane of the MP is not smooth, a square plate with the top plane being smooth is fixed on the MP, as shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 6 Prototype of the 2-axis solar tracker.

Fig. 7 Kinematic calibration of two-axis solar tracker.

Fig. 8 Top plane of the MP. (Left) without plate, (Right) with plate.

The orientation of the w -axis is measured by using a Leica A901 laser tracker. The target ball is respectively fixed at four corners of the square plate in four measurements, and the solar tracker moves to all configurations once in each measurement. Based on the four positions of target balls, the normal vector of

the square plate can be obtained by the LS method and is taken as the measured w .

In the kinematic calibration experiment, measurement and validation configurations are respectively shown as blue and orange dots in Fig. 9. Some validation configurations are even outside the space of measurement configurations, which contributes to the reliability of the experimental results.

For a nominal orientation w of the MP, the measured w before and after calibration are noted as w_0 and w_1 respectively. The estimated w after calibration is defined as w_2 based on the error model. Thus, the orientation errors before and after calibration are Δ_0 and Δ_1 , and the estimated orientation errors is Δ_2 , where $\Delta_i = \arccos(w^T w_i)$. The difference between Δ_1 and Δ_2 is mainly caused by the measurement noise.

The geometric errors are obtained based on the error modeling, measuring and parameter identification proposed in this paper, as shown in Table II. It should be noted that identified errors are estimated values rather than accurate values and the accuracy of identified errors are indirectly validated by the robot accuracy after error compensation.

Based on the identified errors, $\Delta_i, i = 1, 2, 3$ in measurement configurations can be determined, as shown in Fig. 10. It can be found that the maximum w -axis error decreases by about 99% under kinematic calibration. After calibration, the curve Δ_1 is close to Δ_2 , and the difference is less than 0.05 deg.

Similarly, the w -axis errors in validation configurations before and after calibration are obtained. In Fig. 11, it can be found the orientation errors in some validation configurations outside the measurement space are slightly large in the cyan background, while the errors of other validation configurations are close to that of measurement configurations in the purple background. The reason is that: 1) in model fitting problem, the extrapolation prediction accuracy is always worse than the fitting accuracy; 2) the closer to the workspace boundary, the greater the deviation between the error model and the actual physical model.

Table III shows that the maximum orientation errors of the solar tracker are reduced by more than 95% with the kinematic calibration method proposed in this paper. Therefore, the proposed calibration method is validated by the greatly improved accuracy of the solar tracker under kinematic calibration. The work of this paper can also provide a reference for the kinematic calibration of other over-constrained PMs. In this paper, the error constraint equations are obtained based on strict algebraic derivation. Thus, it can be used for other over-constrained mechanisms.

TABLE II
Structural Errors (unit: deg, mm)

δr_{0Ax}	0.38	ω_{2z}	-6.586	δl_{az}	-0.38
δr_{0Az}	-2.77	ω_{3z}	1.513	δl_{asy}	-0.03
δr_{2x}	6.27	ω_{4y}	-1.185	δl_{asz}	-1.54
δr_{2z}	-5.79	$\omega_{\alpha y}$	0.071	δl_{3x}	0.49
δr_{3x}	0.54	$\omega_{\beta y}$	0.062	δl_{3y}	4.04
δr_{4x}	7.37	δl_{hx}	5.71	$\delta l_{\alpha y}$	-5.21
δr_{5x}	2.99	δl_{hy}	-3.17	ω_{bx}	-0.105

δr_{5z}	-3.11	δl_{hz}	2.79	ω_{by}	1.184
ω_{1z}	5.695	δl_{ax}	-1.20	ω_{bz}	-0.935
ω_{2x}	0.150	δl_{ay}	7.80		

Fig. 9 Measurement and validation configurations in calibration.

Fig. 10 Orientation errors in measurement configurations.

Fig. 11 Orientation errors in validation configurations.

TABLE III
Maximum Orientation Error (unit: deg)

Configuration types	Before calibration	After calibration
Measurement	6.827	0.077
Measurement	9.382	0.304

VII. CONCLUSION

The kinematic calibration of a two-axis over-constrained solar tracker is investigated in this paper. A new geometric error model is obtained based on the algebraic approach to strictly derive the error constraint equations in the over-constrained mechanism. It is found that the rotating axes of the 5R PM should still be parallel to each other under geometric errors in the solar tracker. An iterative Tikhonov regularization method which is a prior method with clear physical meaning is presented, and it has better identification stability and accuracy than the LS method and the traditional Tikhonov regularization methods. The experiment results show that the orientation errors of the solar tracker in measurement and validation configurations are reduced by more than 95% with kinematic

calibration, which validate the effectiveness of the proposed calibration method.

However, the work of this paper is also based on two general assumptions in the field of kinematic calibration. These two assumptions are that the robot is rigid and there is no clearance in the joint, which would be gradually eliminated in future research based on this paper.

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